

A novel method for investigating evacuation behavior in urban informal neighborhood, the case of informal urban kampong in Indonesia

*Irsyad Adhi Waskita Hutama⁽¹⁾, Hitoshi Nakamura⁽¹⁾

(1) Graduate School of Engineering and Science, Regional Environment Systems, Shibaura Institute of Technology

*Corresponding author: na21101@shibaura-it.ac.jp

Climate-related disasters such as flooding have vividly impacted the social and economic life of urban habitats, particularly affecting marginalized citizens living in informal urban settlements. Their strategy to adapt to the disaster is simply an on-foot (pedestrian) evacuation. Currently, little is known about the dynamic interplay between individual characteristics, path risk elements, and spatial configuration in shaping specific evacuation behavior in urban informal neighborhood. To understand these interactions, we propose a novel mixed method approaches including: 1) walking evacuation simulation with video approach to capture human interactions with informal built space; 2) dweller' narratives experience collected from walking interviews; 3) computational spatial configurations analysis using space syntax. We demonstrated the proposed mix methods to two contrasting case studies of urban riverbank kampongs in Yogyakarta, Indonesia, questioning their advantages and drawbacks for understanding evacuation behavior in the context of flood disasters. The results suggest the mixed methods excel in numerous ways: 1) collect ground-truth data on individual evacuation behavior at a detailed neighborhood level; 2) relate human and spatial factors in exploring evacuation behavior; 3) voluntary participation of residents as the primary subject of the research. The challenge is that the author must obtain the research consent and trust first to ease the fieldwork for data collection in an informal neighborhood. Adopting the mixed method provided a practical insight into a human-centered perspective in strategizing an effective emergency evacuation for informal urban neighborhoods. In addition, the collected individual behavioral data can be utilized as a starting point to develop an empirical agent-based model to simulate an effective evacuation scenario under various types of hazards (e.g., fire and earthquake).

Keyword: informal urban neighborhood, flooding, a novel mixed method, evacuation behavior, Space syntax, evacuation simulation with video, walking interview